

Uterine Perforation Due to IUD Migration: A Rare Cause of Pneumoperitoneum in an Elderly Female

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Abstract

Background: Intrauterine devices (IUDs) are widely used as a safe and effective form of long-term contraception. Although complications are uncommon, IUD migration and uterine perforation are rare but serious adverse events. These complications can lead to acute abdominal emergencies, including pneumoperitoneum and peritonitis, which may mimic gastrointestinal perforation.

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 71-year-old woman with a history of type 2 diabetes mellitus and a left lower limb fracture, who presented with generalized abdominal pain, nausea, and vomiting. CT imaging revealed free intraperitoneal air (pneumoperitoneum), raising suspicion of gastrointestinal perforation. An emergency exploratory laparotomy was performed. Intraoperative findings revealed purulent peritoneal fluid and a perforation on the posterior wall of the uterus, with the IUD visibly protruding through the uterine serosa. The IUD was surgically removed, and the perforation could not be primarily repaired, and we performed a total hysterectomy. No gastrointestinal pathology was found. The patient recovered well postoperatively.

Conclusion: This case highlights the importance of considering IUD-related uterine perforation in the differential diagnosis of acute abdomen and pneumoperitoneum, even in elderly patients. Timely diagnosis and surgical management are essential to avoid life-threatening complications. Regular follow-up of IUD users, especially postmenopausal women, is critical for early detection of delayed complications.

Introduction

Intrauterine devices (IUDs) particularly levonorgestrel-releasing or copper formulations are a common form of long-acting reversible contraception. While safe, rare complications include uterine perforation and extra-uterine migration [1–3]. Manufacturer guidelines and clinical practice recommend removal of IUDs after menopause due to increased risks such as uterine atrophy and embedment [4–6]. Retained IUDs have been reported in women in their 60s, sometimes causing pelvic pain or bleeding [4,5,7]. However, presentation with pneumoperitoneum, typically indicative of gastrointestinal rupture, is exceedingly rare in this age group, making diagnosis challenging and emphasizing the need for a high index of suspicion.

Case report

A 71-year-old woman with a medical history of type 2 diabetes and a left lower limb fracture sustained 4 years ago presented to the emergency department with a 2 days history of generalized abdominal pain. The pain had worsened progressively, accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and abdominal distension. She denied any recent trauma or abdominal surgery. The patient had an intrauterine device inserted 40 years ago, with no follow up, and kept it after menopause. Upon physical examination, the patient was tachycardic (heart rate 110 bpm) and hypotensive (blood pressure 95/60 mmHg). Abdominal examination revealed generalized tenderness, suggesting peritoneal irritation.

More Information

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CT scan showed pneumoperitoneum with a significantly distended uterus and an IUD in the uterine cavity.

Figure1: CT Images Showing the Pneumoperitoneum and the Foreign Body

Given the clinical signs of acute abdomen, the patient was promptly taken for exploratory laparotomy. Upon incising, we found Pus in the peritoneal cavity, confirming peritonitis and a uterine perforation on the posterior aspect of the uterus, where the IUD had migrated. The IUD was carefully removed and The perforation was large that a primary suture was not possible so we decided to proceed with total hysterectomy.

Figure 2: The IUD Protruding from the Uterus

The peritoneal cavity was irrigated thoroughly with sterile saline, and a drain was placed for postoperative monitoring. No other abdominal pathology or bowel perforation was identified.

Figure 3: The Uterine Specimen with the Large Perforation

The patient was started on broad-spectrum antibiotics and pain management and she was discharged on postoperative day 5, following significant improvement, with instructions for wound care and follow-up appointments.

Discussion

Uterine perforations occur in about 1–2 per 1,000 IUD insertions [2,6]. Mechanisms include immediate perforation at insertion or gradual erosion through the uterine wall, facilitated by atrophy and contractions [3,8,9]. Postmenopausal uterine atrophy increases the risk of delayed penetration [3,5,6].

Pneumoperitoneum typically signals gastrointestinal perforation, but uterine rupture from a retained IUD should be considered, particularly when imaging shows an intrauterine device [1,4]. Previous reports have documented similar findings, though rarely linked with acute peritonitis [9,10].

Cases of retained IUDs in older women show complications such as bleeding, pelvic pain, and infection, especially if the device is embedded [4,5,7–10]. Studies show a high rate of IUD embedment in postmenopausal patients, and delayed removal increases risks [7]. Expert consensus recommends removal of IUDs within 6–12 months after menopause [7].

CT offers accurate identification of device location and surrounding pathology [4]. Non-perforated but migrated IUDs can often be removed laparoscopically; however, laparotomy is warranted in acute peritonitis [9]. In our case, surgery resulted in full recovery.

Conclusion

This case underscores the critical need to remove IUDs after menopause to avoid late complications including perforation and peritonitis. Clinicians should maintain suspicion for uterine perforation and pneumoperitoneum in elderly women with retained IUDs, even decades after insertion. Regular follow-up and timely imaging are essential for preventing life-threatening sequelae.

Statement of Informed Consent

All authors declare that written informed consent was obtained from the patient (or other approved parties) for publication of this case report and accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editorial office/Chief Editor/Editorial Board members of this journal.

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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